

THE CHALLENGES OF ICT IMPLEMENTATION IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ILORIN WEST LOCAL GOVERNMENT

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Abstract

This study is driven towards investigating the challenges of ICT implementation in Secondary Schools in Ilorin West Local Government Area of Kwara State. 100 students were randomly selected for the study. Data collected were sampled using Average Weighted Response (AWR). The study revealed that the challenges facing the implementation of ICT in secondary schools include inadequate funding of ICT facilities, poor maintenance of existing ones, lack of qualified / skilled personnel amongst others.

It is thus recommended that stakeholders in education such as government, school management, public and corporate bodies should contribute to the effective funding of ICT facilities encourage in the job training for computer studies teachers and establish a standard maintenance programme for existing ICT facilities in schools.

INTRODUCTION

ICT stand for Information Communication Technologies and for the purpose as a "diverse set of technological tools and resources used to communicate, and to create, disseminate, store, and manage information" these technologies include computers, the internet, broadcasting technologies and telephony.

Access to information continuously grow exponentially, as such, it is needed in all spheres of life. Information acquisition processing and dissemination are very

important phenomena in the realization of a virile and standard educational output.

The National Committee on ICT (2011) observed that increasing globalised driven ICT makes it imperative for Nigeria as an emerging ICT market to consider the application and promotion of ICT strategy to facilitate its rapid growth and development. This is why in the area of capacity building one of its objectives is to integrate ICT into the national educational curriculum.

The introduction of ICT into school curriculum clearly changes the way education is conducted not only is it possible to work with distance learning and achieve a closer collaboration between different schools, ICT also paves the way for a new pedagogical approach, where students are expected to play more active role than before (Alabi 2004).

ICT has become one of the basic building blocks of the modern society within a very short time. Many countries now included understanding, mastering the basic skills and concept of ICT as part of the core of education alongside reading, writing and numeracy. Furthermore, ICT focuses on the crucial issues of how people communicate and learn in an electronic environment; it actually depends on effective communication of human knowledge whether this occurs in a face to face classroom contact or across the internet.

The role of ICT in the transformation of the education sector cannot be over emphasized, experts conclude that it has some tantalizing characteristics which actually cannot be resisted, for example, they maintain that it has the advantage of interactivity, globalizing and networking in the teaching and learning process. It is observed that with the application of ICT, teaching and learning have been made more effective and less cumbersome.

The use of ICT present teachers and students the opportunity to gather good research materials and even link up with erudite scholars across the globe (Allen, 1994) in Orunkoyi. (2012). There are wide varieties ICTs currently available to schools that can be implemented to enhance both students' and teachers overall

that can enhance both teachers and students' qualitative standards; these tools include; e-mails instant message, chat rooms, facebook, twitter, and other social network websites.

Some benefits of ICT in respect of teachers and students are outlined as follows:

- ICT facilities enhance sharing of resources, expertise and advice
- Higher quality lessons through greater collaboration between teachers in planning and preparing resources.
- Greater efficiency throughout the school
- Regular use of ICT across different curriculum subjects can have a beneficial motivational influence in students' learning
- Encouragement of independent and active learning
- Opportunities to collaborate on assignments with people outside or within the school

Although, ICT has a lot of benefits and advantages, there are some disadvantages which includes high cost of implementation, unskilled personnel and many teachers are unfamiliar with using ICT in the classroom or independently. Teachers are also resistant to incorporating such technologies into their established pedagogies.

However, the experience of introducing different ICT in the classroom and other educational setting over the past several decades suggests that the full realization of the potential educational benefits of ICT is not automotive to succeed, the use of ICT at lower level of education needs to be supported. The available infrastructures for ICT in most secondary schools are grossly inadequate. It was observed that students still visit 'café' because of non availability and too much demand on the internet facility in the school. Olaniyi (2010) opined of most institution in Nigeria have started building their ICT centres but they focus mainly on internet facilities without considering other components that makes up the ICT centres. The inclusion of ICT in schools can assist a long way in contributing to

improving the quality of education at the secondary school level ; thus preparing the students' for greater challenges at higher levels.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study is a descriptive research using survey method.

Sample and Sampling techniques

Sample consist of participating six secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government Area of Kwara State. The schools were randomly selected.

Research Instrument

A research designed questionnaire divided into two parts; section A and B. The Likert scale was used in designing the questionnaire, which has for responses strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), Strongly Disagree (SD). It questionnaire was validated by expert in the field computer science.

Data Analysis

The data collected were analysed using Average Weighted Response (AWR).

Result

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between poor funding and ICT facilities, procurement and maintenance.

Table 1:

Average weighted Response (AWR) on poor funding and ICT facilities procurement, and maintenance.

NO	ITEM	SA (4)	A(3)	D(2)	SD(1)	AWR	R
1	Our Computers are broken down because they are not well maintained.	4 (16)	13 (39)	30 (60)	13 (13)	2.2	N
2	Our computer laboratory is well equipped	8 (32)	37 (111)	53 (106)	20 (20)	2.3	N
3	Computer and internet facilities are very expensive to procure and maintain	24 (96)	27 (81)	6 (12)	2 (2)	3.2	N
4	Inadequate funding affects the effective use of computer laboratory	18 (72)	28 (84)	11 (22)	2 (2)	3.1	S
5	Facilities in the computer laboratory are inadequate to cater for the number of students.	22 (88)	26 (78)	4 (8)	5 (5)	3.0	S
	TAWR					2.8	S

Since TAWR 2.8 falls between 2.6 and 4.0., thus, the research hypothesis is significant; therefore, hypothesis two is rejected.

This means that the procurement of new ICT facilities is often hindered when there is poor funding and this leads to inadequate provision for maintenance of already available facilities and this brings about underutilization of the facilities.

H0₂: there is no significant relationship between ICT implementation and unskilled personnel

Table 2:

AWR on relationship between ICT implementation and unskilled personnel.

NO	ITEM	SA (4)	A(3)	D(2)	SD(1)	AWR	R
1	Computer Science teachers need adequate in-service training for improvement	38 (152)	20 (60)	-	1 (1)	3.0	S
2	Computer Science is a practical oriented subject that requires qualified teachers to handle.	39 (156)	15 (45)	4 (8)	1 (1)	3.6	S
3	I have within the last 3 years attended seminar(s)/ conference(s)/ workshop(s)	11 (44)	15 (45)	23 (46)	10 (10)	2.5	N
4	A computer Science teacher should know how to run installation, maintenance and repair of computer	31 (124)	23 (69)	5 (10)	-	3.4	S
	TAWR					3.3	S

Since TAWR 3.3 falls between 2.6 and 4.0, thus, the research hypothesis is significant; therefore, hypothesis two is rejected.

This means that students' academic performances will be affected negatively when unqualified teachers are employed to teach them. Also the school may end up having degraded ICT system when unskilled ICT personnel are employed to maintain these facilities.

Conclusion and Recommendation

This study was based on investigating challenges facing ICT implementation in secondary schools in Ilorin West. The study find out that poor funding and unskilled personnel are some of the problems facing ICT implementation in secondary schools in Kwara State.

The outcome of first null hypotheses revealed that there is a significant relationship between poor funding and ICT facilities procurement. Therefore the null hypotheses was not accepted. The second null hypotheses in relationship between ICT implementation and unskilled personnel was not accepted. It shows that the implementation of ICT depends on use of skilled, qualified personnel to teach the students.

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It is therefore recommended that government as well as school management should endeavour to produce funds and equipping schools with standard computer laboratories for teaching and learning in secondary school and skilled personnel should be employed by government, school authorities in public and private schools to teach computer studies.

Olaniyi, S.S. (2006): E-learning Technology: Tech Nigeria experience. Shape the Change XXIII FIG. Congress, Munich Germany Oct. 8-13.

Orunkoye, E.G. (2012). Challenges facing the development of ICT in secondary schools in Ilorin West Local Government Area of Kwara State. B.Ed. unpublished project. Kwara State College of Education, Ilorin.

Yusuf, M.O. (2002): Information and Communication Technology, and Education. International Education Journal Vol (6) 3: 316-321
This paper examined the stages of teaching writing in the primary schools. What writing entails, the types of writing, the writing process and spelling, etc were discussed. The paper recommended that teachers should try and get recommended textbooks as this will improve their writing skills. It also recommended that teachers should be allowed to attend seminars, conferences and workshops so as to brainstorm issues on writing.

INTRODUCTION

In Nigeria, English language is one of the core subjects taught in schools. Also, a credit pass in English is one of the prerequisites for admission of students into any higher institution of learning. The ability of the individual students to listen, speak and read well will improve such student's writing skill.

Language as a means of communication has four skills- listening, speaking, reading and writing. Listening and reading are regarded as receptive skills; while speaking and writing are called productive skills. Writing is the process of representing one's thought, ideas and feelings graphically and conventionally. It is considered as the most difficult of all the language skills because the writing process demands for the author's presence of mind in simultaneous thinking, organising and

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